

D10.6 Report on the contribution to standardization

Project ref. no.	Horizon 2020- LC-GV-2018-2019-2020 GA No. 101006844
Project title	Fatigue modelling and fast testing methodologies to optimize part design and to boost lightweight materials deployment in chassis parts
Duration of the project	01/02/2021 – 31/01/2024 (36 months)
WP/Task:	WP10 - Task 10.4 Standardization activities
Document due Date:	31/01/2024
Actual date of delivery	31/01/2024
Leader of this deliverable	UNE
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Document status	Final

Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
1	02/02/2021	Rafael Postigo (UNE)	Pre-draft distributed to partners
2	22/01/2024	Rafael Postigo (UNE)	Approved - Distributed to partners
3	12/03/2024	Sergio Jiménez (CIMNE)	Revision according to PO specifications and resubmission

Executive summary

The Spanish Association for Standardization (UNE), as a European Standardization Body, is a partner in the Fatigue4Light project to provide support regarding the standardization tasks included in the project.

In order to fulfil this commitment, this deliverable, D10.6 “Report on the contribution to standardization”, has been prepared to report the standardization activities developed in order to contribute to the generation of new standards that can facilitate the acceptance, and utilisation by the market of the developed solutions in Fatigue4Light project, as well as to use the standardization system as a tool for dissemination of the project results, and interaction with the market stakeholders.

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006844. The information included here reflects only the author’s view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information.

Table of contents

Deliverable Information sheet.....	2
Executive summary	2
Table of contents	3
List of figures	4
List of tables	5
List of abbreviations	6
Introduction.....	7
• Project Presentation Overview	7
• Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations	7
Scope	7
Definition of the strategy.....	7
First contact with the standardization technical committees	8
Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees.....	9
Standardization process.....	10

List of figures

Figure 1 – Strategy for the contribution to standardization of Fatigue4Light 8

List of tables

N/A

List of abbreviations

In this document the following abbreviations and acronyms could be used, and in this list, they are indicated with its meaning:

UNE	Spanish Association for Standardization
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC (CLC)	European Committee for Standardization in the Electrical field
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
CWA	CEN or CENELEC Workshop Agreement
WS	CEN or CENELEC Workshop
EAD	European Assessment Document
EN	European Standard
EOTA	European Organisation for Technical Assessment
ESO	European Standardisation Organisation
ETAG	European Technical Approval Guideline
hEN	Harmonised European Standard
ISO	International Organization for Standardization; International Standard
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
NMC	National Mirror Committee
NSB	National Standardization Body
SC	Subcommittee
TC	Technical Committee
TR	Technical Report
TS	Technical Specification
WG	Working Group
WI	Work Item
ASD-STAN	AeroSpace and Defence Industries Association of Europe. Standardization
AECMA	European Association of Aerospace Industries

Introduction

- **Project Presentation Overview**

Fatigue4Light project aims to investigate lightweight solutions adapted to the chassis part of EV to reach a 24-30% weight reduction. This provides a 12-15% weight saving from structural vehicle weight and increases EV safety due to reduced sprung mass. Solutions are based on the introduction of especially developed material solutions with high fatigue performance (AHSS, stainless steel, Al alloys and hybrid metal-FRP materials), the development of new computer modelling with high fatigue prediction accuracy and new experimental methodologies that reduce the testing time.

Sustainability of the proposed solutions are continuously considered along project through an eco-design general approach. Environmental assessments through LCA, affordability based in LCC as well as social inclusion thanks to the recovery of CRMs from alternative waste streams allow endowing Fatigue4Light into a novelty circular dimension. Attention are given to manufacturing processes (cutting and welding) to improve the knowledge on their effect to the overall fatigue performance of chassis components. Six lab scale and industrial demonstrators are defined to validate the proposed solutions.

The fatigue model is verified on demonstrators and then used in a virtual testing process to assess the weight reduction potential of the proposed materials, together with a redesign process oriented to lightweight the components while ensuring structural integrity. The Project reduces lead times to market due to the developed model and advanced fatigue testing methodologies and standardization will be followed.

The final outcome is to give modelling and experimental tools for the lightweighting process on chassis parts subjected to fatigue. Clear and practical guidelines are established with respect to different factors: eco design with proposed materials, advanced modelling approaches and the influence of forming processes on part performance.

- **Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations**

The deliverable is fully in line with the contractual obligations and the project objectives. There is no time and content deviation.

Scope

This deliverable D10.6 “Report on the contribution to standardization” defines a strategy for the contribution to standardization from Fatigue4Light, which includes the steps towards a successful contribution to standardization, and the actions done until the date of submission of the deliverable for fulfilling such strategy.

Definition of the strategy

The contribution to standardization of Fatigue4Light is based in the interaction with the relevant Standardization Technical Committees and in the initiation of a standardization process. The strategy comprises the actions represented in the next figure:

Figure 1 – Strategy for the contribution to standardization of Fatigue4Light

First contact with the standardization technical committees

The objectives of this first contact is to raise awareness about Fatigue4Light among the relevant standardization committees and to ease subsequent contacts. Different categories of stakeholders at European/International level are present in these committees, so the standardization system is used as a targeted dissemination channel. Feedback is asked to gather any view, opinion or advise about the project and the standardization possibilities or needs. Additionally, these first contacts are useful to determine the best path towards the initiation of a standardization process, moreover this first step ease future contacts if this process is launched within a standardization committee.

In this sense, awareness of the Fatigue4Light project and its aims and main outcomes has been done through the following technical committees of standardization both at International and European level:

European Committees:

- CEN/TC 132, Aluminium and aluminium alloys
- ASD-STAN/D 4, Materials
- CEN/TC 249, Plastics
- CEN/TC 459, ECISS - European Committee for Iron and Steel Standardization
- CEN/TC 459/SC 1, Test methods for steel (other than chemical analysis)
- CEN/TC 459/SC 3, Structural steels other than reinforcements

- CEN/TC 459/SC 9, Coated and uncoated flat products to be used for cold forming
- CEN/TC 459/SC 11, Steel castings and forgings
- CEN/SS M11, Pulvimetalurgy
- CEN/WS, Fateda

International Committees:

- ISO/TC 17/SC 11, Steel castings
- ISO/TC 164/SC 4, Fatigue, fracture and toughness testing
- ISO/TC 22, Road vehicles
- ISO/TC 22/SC 33, Vehicle dynamics and chassis components
- ISO/TC 22/SC 37, Electrically propelled vehicles
- ISO/TC 17, Steel

These committees are the ones that previously were identified within the standardization framework as the most relevant related to the scope of Fatigue4Light project.

Subsequent interaction with the standardization technical committees

Different relationships can be established with the relevant CEN/CENELEC, ISO/IEC technical committees. Two factors determine the more suitable interactions: the impact/relevance of the standardization works of the standardization committees and the feasibility of initiating a standardization process within a standardization committee (versus initiating the standardization process within a standardization workshop, details are given below). The ways of interaction of the project with the standardization committees include:

1. Follow-up the activity of the relevant standardization committees. This allows to detect the initiation of standardization works that can be relevant for Fatigue4Light and the progress of significant existing under-development standards.
2. Further contact with the standardization committees to update the progress of Fatigue4Light. This is achievable by delivering reports, by attending relevant technical committees' meetings or by joint events. On the one hand, this action contributes to further dissemination of the project and can guide the initiation of the standardization process, on the other hand this further contact is mandatory towards the standardization committees directly covering (if it where the case) the subject promoted by Fatigue4Light to undergo a standardization process.
3. The participation of one or more Fatigue4Light partners in the standardization technical committees. Standardization is an open activity, and all interested parties may participate in the technical committees through the designation of their National Standardization Body. This option allows for a deeper follow-up of the activity of a standardization committee and is valuable if the standardization process is going to be initiated within the standardization committee.
4. The establishment of a formal liaison of Fatigue4Light with the standardization committees. It is recommended only when the work of the standardization committee is closely linked with the main goals of the project and a direct technical contribution from the project is expected.

In this sense, the main action developed has been the follow-up of the activity of the relevant standardization committees, in particular -ISO/TC 164/SC 4, Fatigue, fracture and toughness

testing, which is the one that finally is the most impacted by Fatigue4Light standardization process.

Standardization process

The main objective of the standardization activities in Fatigue4Light is to facilitate the market acceptance of the results by transferring these results and findings to standards that have a wide recognition in the market. With the collaboration of the relevant partners the feasible results to go through a standardization process will be identified. Different options to contribute to standardization shall be considered depending on the kind of the results (nature, availability and IPR) and the standardization context (existence of closely related standards and reactions of the standardization committees):

1. Development of a new standard within a standardization workshop. A standardization workshop is a group of entities with a common interest in developing a standard about a specific issue. It is the equivalent figure to the standardization committee, but the number of participants is typically smaller and the working procedures faster and more flexible. A standardization workshop is created when there is a need of developing a precise standard in an innovative field that is not covered by the existing standardization committees or when these committees are not interested in developing such standard (e.g. it does not fit in their work programme). If the subject is close to the field covered by a standardization committee it shall be informed and allow for the launching of the standardization workshop.

Considering that the standardization workshop option is interesting for Fatigue4Light mainly in the European environment, the standardization workshop will be named hereinafter as CEN Workshop or CENELEC Workshop. The standard produced by a CEN/CENELEC Workshop is called CEN Workshop Agreement or CENELEC Workshop Agreement, typically named as CWA. The nature and timeline for the development of CWAs is very suitable for the framework of the R&I projects.

2. Standardization within a standardization committee. It may be interesting or needed that the results of Fatigue4Light to go through the standardization process are standardized within a standardization committee. The possible scenarios are:
 - Development of a new standard within a standardization committee. When there is a result of Fatigue4Light to be promoted to a standard in a field covered by a standardization committee and such committee decides to include this development in its work programme. The resulting standard would have the support of the standardization committee but the work shall be adapted to the internal timeline of such standardization committee and could go beyond the timeframe of the project.
 - Contribute to an on-going standard. As a consequence of the monitoring of the standardization landscape it may be found that the results of Fatigue4Light are covered by an on-going standard but that these results do not fit in the current draft of the standard. Gaps in standards may be found in both, standards that are being developed from a new initiative and standards already published that are going under a review process towards a new version.
 - Request the modification of a standard that is not under development or review. The gap may be found also in published standards that are not under any work within the standardization committee. In this case, a fully justified modification request can be made to the standardization committee.

- Outline of a future standard. Only when there is not a clear view on a full roadmap for the contribution to standardization (like lack of agreement within the Consortium or lack of the expected results).

In this sense, after discussed these different options and taking to account the timing of the project, it was decided to follow the creation of standardization workshop at CEN level with the aim of developing at least a CWA on the subjects of Fatigue4Light more suitable for being introduced in CEN standardization framework.

The candidate subjects identified in Fatigue4Light and the related deliverables which could be the basis for further CWAs were the following:

D1.2 Eco-design of Fatigue4Light materials. WP1 (EUT) Public M15

D2.1 Advanced fatigue testing methods. WP2 (AMMR-EUT) Confidential, M7

D5.1 Health monitoring techniques for chassis parts. WP5 (RISE) Public M24

D7.1 Virtual testing on LDEV and HDV parts and EV wheels. WP7 (CRF) Confidential M33

D8.1 Lightweight potential and performance the solutions analysed. WP8 (CIMNE) Confidential M36

After some discussions regarding the topics content, its the relation with the existing CEN technical committees, the timing for the standardization process and the novelties of such topics, it was agreed that D2.1 Advanced fatigue testing methods, was the most suitable output of Fatigue4Light for becoming in a CWA. In fact, since two different quick and advanced fatigue testing methods were developed, it had sense to develop two CWA for such methods.

After this decision, the process of creating and starting the related CEN Workshop (WS) started. A WS proposal, a WS project plan were produced and submitted to CEN—CENELEC central secretariat for the diffusion of this initiative and provide the possibility of all the interested parties to be involve in the WS.

**Approved Project plan for the
CEN Workshop on "
Fatigue4Light advanced and
fast fatigue testing methods"**

**Requests to participate in the Workshop
and/or comments on the project plan are
to be submitted by 2023-09-14 to
rpostigo@une.org¹**

Recipients of this project plan are kindly requested to name all patent rights known to them to be relevant to the Workshop and to make available all supporting documents.

Manresa, 2023-09-22

¹ Applications for participating in the Workshop and comments on the project plan that are not received by the deadline do not need to be taken into consideration. Once constituted, the Workshop will decide whether or not to consider the comments received in good time.

In this regard, a specific web site at [CEN Web](#) was created:

This CEN/WS intends to develop two CWAs (Workshop Agreement). The planned Workshop intends to deliver 2 different documents related to obtaining in a limited time the materials fatigue properties. The first one, so called self-heating measurements, is based on the evolution of temperature measurements under cyclic loading. The second one, so called stiffness method measurements, is based on the evolution of the damage during cyclic loading.

Their titles and scopes of the envisioned CWAs are the following:

- **CWA 1: Fatigue testing. Self-heating measurements**

The planned CEN Workshop Agreement establishes a testing methodology to determine the fatigue limit at shorter times and with a reduced number of specimens, by the evolution of the temperature of the specimen during cyclic loading to estimate the fatigue properties.

The planned CEN Workshop Agreement is applicable to the materials considered within Fatigue4light project. Hence, AHSS, stainless steel, Al alloys and hybrid metal-FRP materials.

- **CWA 2: Fatigue testing. Rapid fatigue testing by damage control.**

The planned CEN Workshop Agreement establishes a testing methodology to determine the fatigue limit at shorter times and with a reduced number of specimens, by the evolution of the stiffness of the specimen under cyclic loading.

The planned CEN Workshop Agreement is applicable to the materials considered within Fatigue4light project. Hence, AHSS, stainless steel, Al alloys and hybrid metal-FRP materials.

The kick-off meeting will be held on **Friday 22 September 2023**. The kick-off meeting will be in CCMC but hybrid. Online access will be provided in the invitation.

All interested parties are invited to submit their **registration form** and the **comments on the draft Project Plan** to Workshop Secretary, Mr Rafael POSTIGO, rpostigo@une.org by **10 September 2023**. You are **kindly requested to use the commenting form** below.

The final deliverable of this Workshop (CEN/CWA) is expected to be finalized in February 2024.

Download the documents:

- [Draft Project Plan](#) (pdf format)
- [Kick-off meeting agenda](#) (pdf format)
- [Commenting form](#) (word format)
- [Registration form](#) (word format)

The WS kick off meeting was held on 22nd of September of 2023, In this meeting the project plan for developing two CWA:

- **CWA 1: Fatigue testing. Self-heating measurements;**
- **CWA 2: Fatigue testing. Rapid fatigue testing by damage control.**

Was approved, and a Chairman (Sergio Jimenez from CIMNE) and a Secretary (Rafael Postigo from UNE) were appointed. Up to five different organizations has been registered for being part of the WS:

- CIMNE;
- INSTRON;
- EURECAT;
- GESTAMP;
- RISE.

Particularly, INSTRON representative take part of ISO/TC 164/SC 4, Fatigue, fracture and toughness testing, working as convenor of a working group of this technical committee in the subject of testing instrumentation for fatigue testing. This technical committee was identified as the most impacted in the framework of standardization by Fatigue4Light Project.

Finally, in the kick off meeting was decided the organization of the technical work.

Since then, four meetings have been held (Including kick-off one):

- Kick off – 2023-09-22
- 2023-11-13
- 2023-12-18
- 2024-01-15

During this period, the two CWA were registered in the CEN Projex Online which is the data base and portal of the CEN work program:

The screenshot shows the CEN Projex Online interface for the CEN/WS FAT4LI work program. The page title is "CEN/WS FAT4LI" and the description is "Fatigue4Light advanced and fast fatigue testing methods". The status is "Active", the secretariat is "UNE", and the secretary is "Mr R. Postigo (rpostigo@une.org) (Appointed on 2023-09-07)". The CCMC PM is "Mr K. Alairy".

Below the details, there is a table of work items:

WI Number	Reference	Title	WI Status	Standard Status	Last Milestone
WSF4L001	prCWA	Advanced fatigue testing methods — Part 1: Self-heating measurements	Active	Not Published	10.99.0000
WSF4L002	prCWA	Advanced fatigue testing methods — Part 2: Stiffness method	Active	Not Published	10.99.0000

And two draft CWA were developed and circulated for comments by the WS participants:

<p style="text-align: right;">CEN/TC XXX Date: 2023-12 prCWA XXXXX-1:2023 Secretariat: UNE</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Advanced fatigue testing methods — Part 1: Self-heating measurements</p> <p style="text-align: center; margin-top: 100px;">CCMC will prepare and attach the official title page.</p>	<table border="0"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align: left;">Contents</th> <th style="text-align: right;">Page</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>European foreword.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">3</td></tr> <tr><td>Introduction.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">4</td></tr> <tr><td>1 Scope.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">5</td></tr> <tr><td>2 Normative references.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">5</td></tr> <tr><td>3 Abbreviations.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">5</td></tr> <tr><td>4 General.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">5</td></tr> <tr><td>5 Self-heating measurements.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">6</td></tr> <tr><td>5.1 Self-heating procedure.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">6</td></tr> <tr><td>5.1.1 Geometry of the specimen.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">6</td></tr> <tr><td>5.1.2 Temperature measurement.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">7</td></tr> <tr><td>5.1.3 Testing protocol [10].....</td><td style="text-align: right;">9</td></tr> <tr><td>5.2 Determination of the mean endurance limit.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">12</td></tr> <tr><td>5.3 Two scales probabilistic model.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">12</td></tr> <tr><td>5.4 Identification of the model parameters.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">13</td></tr> <tr><td>5.5 Building of an S-N-P curve.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">14</td></tr> <tr><td>6 Materials of interest.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">16</td></tr> <tr><td>Bibliography.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">17</td></tr> </tbody> </table> <p style="text-align: center; margin-top: 20px;">2</p>	Contents	Page	European foreword.....	3	Introduction.....	4	1 Scope.....	5	2 Normative references.....	5	3 Abbreviations.....	5	4 General.....	5	5 Self-heating measurements.....	6	5.1 Self-heating procedure.....	6	5.1.1 Geometry of the specimen.....	6	5.1.2 Temperature measurement.....	7	5.1.3 Testing protocol [10].....	9	5.2 Determination of the mean endurance limit.....	12	5.3 Two scales probabilistic model.....	12	5.4 Identification of the model parameters.....	13	5.5 Building of an S-N-P curve.....	14	6 Materials of interest.....	16	Bibliography.....	17
Contents	Page																																				
European foreword.....	3																																				
Introduction.....	4																																				
1 Scope.....	5																																				
2 Normative references.....	5																																				
3 Abbreviations.....	5																																				
4 General.....	5																																				
5 Self-heating measurements.....	6																																				
5.1 Self-heating procedure.....	6																																				
5.1.1 Geometry of the specimen.....	6																																				
5.1.2 Temperature measurement.....	7																																				
5.1.3 Testing protocol [10].....	9																																				
5.2 Determination of the mean endurance limit.....	12																																				
5.3 Two scales probabilistic model.....	12																																				
5.4 Identification of the model parameters.....	13																																				
5.5 Building of an S-N-P curve.....	14																																				
6 Materials of interest.....	16																																				
Bibliography.....	17																																				

<p style="text-align: right;">CEN/TC XXX Date: 2023-12 prCWA XXXXX-2:2023 Secretariat: UNE</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Advanced fatigue testing methods — Part 2: Stiffness method measurements</p> <p style="text-align: center; margin-top: 100px;">CCMC will prepare and attach the official title page.</p>	<p style="text-align: left; margin-bottom: 10px;">prCWA XXXXX-2:2023 (E)</p> <table border="0"> <thead> <tr> <th style="text-align: left;">Contents</th> <th style="text-align: right;">Page</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr><td>European foreword.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">3</td></tr> <tr><td>Introduction.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">4</td></tr> <tr><td>1 Scope.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">5</td></tr> <tr><td>2 Normative references.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">5</td></tr> <tr><td>3 Abbreviations.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">5</td></tr> <tr><td>4 Stiffness method measurements.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">5</td></tr> <tr><td>4.1 Stiffness method procedure.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">7</td></tr> <tr><td>4.1.1 Testing conditions for metallic materials.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">7</td></tr> <tr><td>4.1.2 Testing conditions for composite and hybrid materials.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">9</td></tr> <tr><td>4.2 Three regimes approach.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">11</td></tr> <tr><td>4.3 Identification of the fatigue properties.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">14</td></tr> <tr><td>5 Materials of interest.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">15</td></tr> <tr><td>Bibliography.....</td><td style="text-align: right;">16</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	Contents	Page	European foreword.....	3	Introduction.....	4	1 Scope.....	5	2 Normative references.....	5	3 Abbreviations.....	5	4 Stiffness method measurements.....	5	4.1 Stiffness method procedure.....	7	4.1.1 Testing conditions for metallic materials.....	7	4.1.2 Testing conditions for composite and hybrid materials.....	9	4.2 Three regimes approach.....	11	4.3 Identification of the fatigue properties.....	14	5 Materials of interest.....	15	Bibliography.....	16
Contents	Page																												
European foreword.....	3																												
Introduction.....	4																												
1 Scope.....	5																												
2 Normative references.....	5																												
3 Abbreviations.....	5																												
4 Stiffness method measurements.....	5																												
4.1 Stiffness method procedure.....	7																												
4.1.1 Testing conditions for metallic materials.....	7																												
4.1.2 Testing conditions for composite and hybrid materials.....	9																												
4.2 Three regimes approach.....	11																												
4.3 Identification of the fatigue properties.....	14																												
5 Materials of interest.....	15																												
Bibliography.....	16																												

Comments were received and discussed in a specific meeting (2023-12-15), where decision were made on the implementation of each of them.

At the date of this deliverable, the WS is working on the revision of the two draft CWA in order to implement these comments within an improved text.

The aim of the WS is to get ready for publication at the end of February 2024 these standard documents and be available for the society in the CEN web free of charge. In this manner, the society can benefit from Fatigue4Light project outcomes.